

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Rakhmatullayeva Dilobar Erkinovna

**DIGITAL GAME BASED LEARNING IN SECOND LANGUAGE: THE
INFLUENCE OF VIDEOGAMES IN LEARNING VOCABULARY**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

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